

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYURETHANE CELLULAR FOAM FROM PALM CANOPY POWDER

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ABSTRACT

Polyurethane cellular foam mixed palm canopy powder were fabricated with sized 350 mm x 350 mm x 100 mm (W x L x H), and were used as heat insulator. Palm canopy powder of three various sizes: 100 mesh, 150 mesh and 200 mesh, respectively, to the polyurethane in the following proportions of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 percent. The mechanical properties was conducted which includes bending test and tensile test in order to study the possibility of using a combination of palm canopy powder and polyurethane foam to produce heat insulation board. According to the results, the proportions of palm canopy powder are affected to the level of bending strength of the material. The maximum bending strength found was 2.56 kilopascal when added palm canopy powder sized 100 mesh in the proportions of 5 percent whereas the minimum bending strength was 1.65 kilopascal when added palm canopy powder sized 200 mesh in the proportions of 30 percent. The proportions of palm canopy powder, however, did not affect the level of Tensile Strength of the material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Heat insulation is highly essential for hot climate region as global temperature continues to rise due to the current global warming, resulting in an increasing energy consumption among buildings, industrial factories, and households in maintaining certain temperature level within buildings. Heat insulation is generally made from synthetic materials such as aluminum foil, fiberglass foam, and rock wool. These materials are difficult to dispose or even naturally decompose, which poses threat to our environment and health [1]. Hence, unused material and agricultural materials are expected to be

alternatively used for producing heat insulation in the future. Recently, many researches have been developed the natural material to be used in combination with other materials for producing heat insulation [2-4].

Palme is another important cash crop as its oil contains various uses in our daily life. Palm oil is commonly used among households and restaurants in cooking as well as manufacturing process of instant noodle product, margarine, etc. It is also often used as an ingredient for producing soap, toothpaste, dish washing soap, cosmetic and skincare products [5]. These different uses of palm oil mostly derive from the processing of palm fruits and seeds. Normally, palm tree will produce approximately 12 fruit bunches annually, each fruit bunch generally weighs between 10-13 kg and contains 500-4,000 palm fruits. For newly grown palm trees, a large quantity of fruit bunch will be produced.

In this research interesting study the possibility of using a combination of palm canopy powder and polyurethane foam to produce heat insulation board. Prior to its application, natural material must be properly prepared before molding. Before fabrication the polyurethane cellular foam from palm canopy powder, the powder must be treated with 15% wt Sodium_Hydroxide (NaOH) to generate chemical reaction for 30 minutes. The mechanical properties was conducted following standard specification for cellulosic fiber insulating board which includes bending test and tensile test [6-7].

2 EXPERIMENTATION

Palm canopy from palm trees were cut into pieces about 20 centimeter long as shown in Figure 1. Then, the cut palm canopies were boiled in 15% wt Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) for 30 minutes to soften the fibers and produce pores along the surface of palm canopy. This will allow palm canopy powder show better bonding with polyurethane foam. After 30 minutes, palm canopies were rinsed with clean water and sundried until it became completely dried. Then it was heated in the oven to remove moisture before undergoing milling process to make palm powder. Next, palm powder was sorted into three different sizes using Size Sorting Machine as shown in Figure 2a. Palm powder was separated into three sizes of 100, 150, and 200 mesh. To form palm powder-mixed polyurethane foam, polyol was mixed with diisocyanate in 1:1 ratio by weight. Once polyurethane foam was formed, palm canopy powder was added in the proportions of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 percent using steel mold sized 350 x 350 x 100 millimeter. Before preparing primer mixture using plastic plate to prevent contact between mold block surface and heat insulation, palm powder must first be properly mixed in polyurethane foam before pouring the mixture into molding block as shown in Figure 2b. The mixture was kept in the closed mold for 30 minute to prevent mixture expansion as shown in Figure 2c. The Insulation board from polyurethane cellular foam mixed palm canopy powder and it will be cut for mechanical properties testing with bending test and tensile test according to ASTM D 1037 Standard.

Figure 1. Palm three, fruit and canopy

Figure 2 The process for fabrication the polyurethane cellular foam from palm canopy powder

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The test results of mechanical strength of polyurethane foam with palm powder mixture were analyzed by comparing the results of bending test and tensile test. Bending test of polyurethane foam was performed according to ASTM D 1037 standard by first adding palm powder in different proportions and comparing the results to non-composite material as shown in Figure 3. For 100-mesh palm powder (Figure 3a), 150-mesh palm powder (Figure 3b), and 200-mesh palm powder (Figure 3c), it can be observed that once the proportions of palm powder added had been increased, the bending strength of the material tend to decrease in all three sizes of palm powder whereas the bending strength of non-composite material remained at 2.67 kilopascal. From Figure 3, the maximum bending strength of material after adding 200-mesh palm powder in 5 percent proportions by weight is 2.65 kilopascal whereas the maximum values when 150-mesh and 100-mesh palm powder were added in the same

proportions of 5 percent are 2.57 and 2.50 kilopascal, respectively. Once the proportions of palm powder added had been increased, a decreasing trend of bending strength of the material can be observed. At 30 percent proportions of 200-mesh palm powder added, the minimum bending strength measured is 1.65 kilopascal whereas the minimum bending strength measured after adding 100-mesh and 150-mesh palm powder in the same proportions are 1.85 and 1.68 kilopascal, respectively.

Tensile test of polyurethane foam was performed according to ASTM D 1037 Standard by adding different proportions of palm powder and then compared the results with non-composite material as shown in Figure 4 in which palm powder were added with sizes 100, 150 and 200 respectively. The results revealed decreasing tensile strength of composite polyurethane foam whereas the tensile strength of non-composite polyurethane foam remained at 2, 204.33 kilopascal. From Figure 4a, once 100-mesh palm powder was added to polyurethane foam by 5 percent proportions, the maximum tensile strength measured is 2, 139.33 kilopascal and the number tends to drop when the proportions of palm powder had been increased. When 30 percent palm powder was added, tensile strength of 955 kilopascal can be measured. The same pattern can be observed when added 150-mesh palm powder as shown in Figure 4b. At 5 percent palm powder, tensile strength measured is 2,204.33 kilopascal and the number reduced to 802.67 kilopascal when 30 percent palm powder was added. In the case of 200-mesh palm powder (Figure 4c), the same pattern can also be observed when adding 100 and 150 mesh of palm powder. Tensile strength measured at 5 percent proportions of palm powder is 2,183.67 kilopascal and 1,076.33 kilopascal at 30 percent palm powder.

The proportions of palm canopy powder did not affect tensile strength because the specimens were cut along the surface of foam composite which is perpendicular to the plane of force placed on the specimens. Hence, the quantity of palm canopy fibers did not affect tensile strength, despite the fact that each formula contains different amount of palm canopy fibers.

4 CONCLUSION

The proportions of palm powder added to polyurethane foam affected the bending strength of composite material since the increasing amount of palm canopy in heat insulation had affected the structure of the material, causing it to become less homogenous. The proportions of palm powder added, however, did not affect tensile strength of heat insulation board according to the analysis results using one –way anova Analysis at significance level of 0.05 . The results of Bending Test and Tensile Test of polyurethane foam added with three different sizes of palm powder: 100 mesh, 150 mesh and 200 mesh, all displayed corresponding pattern or tendency. In other words, the values of bending strength and tensile strength are at its maximum when added with 5 percent palm powder and at its minimum when added with 30 percent palm powder.

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a) Palm canopy powder 100-mesh

b) Palm canopy powder 150-mesh

c) Palm canopy powder 200-mesh

Figure 3. Bending strengths of heat insulation when added different proportions

a) Palm canopy powder 100-mesh

b) Palm canopy powder 150-mesh

c) Palm canopy powder 200-mesh

Figure 4. Tensile strengths of heat insulation when added different proportions

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